

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

INTEGRATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES AND SOCIAL MEDIA INTO THE METHODOLOGY OF DEVELOPING CREATIVE ACTIVITY IN TEENAGERS

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Abstract

This article is devoted to the study of the experience of using Internet platforms and social media in the process of teaching acting skills and developing creative activity in teenagers. The article analyses the peculiarities of using various online formats, as well as interaction through social networks within theatrical studios. The author considers the possibilities of adapting classic acting teaching methods for work in the virtual environment, and also presents examples of successful practices and innovative approaches to teaching acting skills using modern technologies.

Keywords: information technologies, e-learning, creative activity of teenagers, theatre-studio.

In the modern society and rapidly changing world, the development of creative abilities and activity of teenagers is becoming increasingly important, as it is a crucial factor in raising successful and harmonious individuals. Theatrical education, as one of the forms of extracurricular education, contributes to the realisation of individual talents and interests of the younger generation, as well as to the development of socio-cultural competence and communication skills. With the development of information technology and the expansion of possibilities offered by online platforms, there is a need to adapt classical approaches to teaching acting skills to new conditions. Therefore, the search for and implementation of innovative methods and forms of working with teenagers aimed at fostering their creative activity and developing acting skills using modern technologies and internet resources becomes a pressing task.

The article presents the results of an analysis of the activities of the exemplary theatre-studio «Glagol» that uses internet platforms and social networks in its pedagogical practice. Therefore, this study contributes to the expansion of the pedagogical possibilities of theatre studios and institutions of additional education for children in the development of creative and active teenage personalities, as well as in teaching acting skills using modern information and communication technologies.

The development of a creatively active personality in teenagers is an important task of modern educational systems. Supplementary education and theatre studios can provide additional opportunities for the development of teenagers' creative potential. The use of information technology and e-learning can also contribute to the formation of creative abilities and personal development. Information technology and e-learning can be used in supplementary education and theatre studios to improve the learning process, create interactive educational materials, and enhance feedback quality between teachers and students. Additionally, the use of social networks and online platforms can promote the dissemination and popularisation of theatrical arts among a wider audience and attract new participants.

According to the Federal Law «The Education in the Russian Federation» dated December 29, 2012 No. 273-FZ (as amended on April 30, 2021), *e-learning* is

defined as the organisation of educational activities using information contained in databases and information technologies, technical means, as well as information and telecommunications networks that provide transmission of this information and interaction between students and teachers in the implementation of educational programs. *Information technology* is a set of methods, tools and processes designed for processing, storing, transmitting and receiving information using computer technology and telecommunications networks [3].

Creative active personality of a teenager (CAPT) is a person with a developed creative potential, capable of self-expression, self-realization, and self-improvement through various types of creative activities [1].

Moreover, the importance of developing the creative potential and activity of teenagers, the use of modern information technologies and online resources in teaching acting and theatre arts in general is becoming increasingly necessary. It is important to create conditions for individual self-realization of teenagers in creative activities, which can be provided in the context of supplementary education (theatre studio).

One of such conditions for developing a creative and active personality in teenagers can be the effective use of information technology and social media. In the modern world, there are many online platforms and internet resources that promote the development of teenagers' creative potential, such as master classes, video tutorials, online readings, and other formats [2].

Thus, one of the actively developing forms of work for the exemplary theatre studio «Glagol» is electronic interaction with the audience. For example, a group was created on the social network VKontakte (as a universal internet hosting), where news (#Glagol_chronicles), teasers, and video reports on the studio's activities are regularly posted; online contests (#Gluhoj_Glagol) are held; podcasts (#Listen_to_Glagol) and online readings are published. An online project #Culture_for_the_Masses has been launched by us, within which articles written by students, cultural and educational videos, as well as information about new exhibitions, performances and cultural life of Voronezh are published.

During the mass transition to e-learning caused by quarantine measures in Russia, it was decided to create a series of short studies dedicated to the difficulties of teenagers' lives in new realities, called #Glagol_at_home. After the successful implementation of this initiative, task categories for independent work of students were developed and published on various online platforms in order to implement the educational program.

The "VKontakte Clips" platform has become an ideal platform for working with etudes. This platform allows recording short videos and provides a rich set of tools for editing of any complexity: masks, filters, effects, transitions, etc. In this virtual world, vertical sketches become the content. For Glagol, "Clips" has become a training base before working on more ambitious projects. As part of the #Culture_for_Masses project, we use this social platform to publish experimental rubrics, such as parodies of theatrical life, backstage videos, as well as participating in various theatrical challenges and flash mobs. In the process of working on these sketches, teenagers not only learn the basics of acting, but also develop communication skills, self-expression, and creative thinking. Ultimately, this contributes to the development of CAPT, ready for professional theatre creativity. In addition, this format of work helps teenagers to improve their skills in the field of visual arts, as this social network provides ample opportunities for experiments with various editing tools.

One of the key elements of theatrical art is metamorphosis, the transformation of a stage image. Recently, cosplay, the practice of costume play, has become increasingly popular, allowing people to transform themselves into famous characters from cartoons and movies. In the framework of the rubric #Cosplay_Glagol', students can independently choose their stage image, work on creating costumes and makeup, and then publish their photos and videos. Participation in the cosplay movement and creating stage images is an important mechanism for developing creative activity and self-realization among teenagers. In addition, such projects help to reveal the individual potential of the students, develop teamwork skills, and improve self-esteem and self-discipline, which is an important factor in educating CAPT.

As a part of the #Culture_for_the_Masses project on the YouTube platform, the #Read_Glagol project was launched, aimed at staging mono-performances based on folk tales from around the world. To date, over 80 different releases have been published, in which the entire creative potential of the team has been involved: shadow-theatre, puppet theatre, musicals, pantomimes, cartoons, 2D projections, original fairy tales, and much more. The project involved not only members of the theatre-studio, but also their relatives, friends, and subscribers. The project also has its offshoots — #Theater_Outside_theater, within which, to date, more than 15 videos have been shot to bard songs and 4 short films. The implementation of this project is an effective means of developing the creative activity of adolescents and developing their creative abilities. This project stimulates the development of the participants' creative abilities and imagination. In addition, it allows

teenagers to master the technique of acting, costume and makeup creation, as well as work with video and sound equipment in practice.

Thus, this article has examined various aspects of using digital technologies and social networks in the process of cultivating the creative activity of adolescents. It was established that extracurricular education (theatre-studio) is an important mechanism for shaping creative activity. Examples of using social networks in theatrical creativity of adolescents were considered, which allows them to express their creative individuality and receive feedback from the audience.

The use of digital technologies and social networks in the methodology of nurturing talented and gifted children allows for expanding opportunities for individual self-realization and developing creative thinking. This stimulates participation in various projects, enriches horizons, and expands communicative possibilities. It is important to create conditions for integrating digital technologies into the educational process, which will increase the effectiveness of education, motivate learners, and develop their skills in using modern technology. However, it is necessary to consider that digital technologies do not completely replace traditional methods of education and nurturing, but rather serve as an additional tool for achieving goals. Additionally, it is important to remember the need for support from parents and society in integrating digital technologies into the educational process, as well as protecting children from potential negative consequences of using digital technologies and social networks.

In conclusion, it can be noted that the integration of digital technologies and social networks into the methodology of fostering creative activity in adolescents is a promising direction in the educational process. This approach allows for actively involving adolescents in cultural life, giving them the opportunity to feel part of a creative community, develop their potential, and unleash their talents in accordance with modern requirements and challenges of the time.

References

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